

1 Flexibility of cell fates and functions across sex determination

2 systems revealed by comparative single-cell analyses

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18 ABSTRACT

19 Sex determination in vertebrates can be initiated by a wide range of genetic or
20 environmental triggers. Yet, the degree to which gonadal cell types and genetic programs
21 are conserved remains unresolved. Here we employed single-cell transcriptomics to
22 characterize the temperature-dependent sex determination (TSD) program in gonads from
23 the turtle species *Trachemys scripta*. Comparative analyses against species with genetic sex
24 determination, like mouse (XY) and chicken (ZW), revealed a marked divergence in cell type
25 repertoires and functions during vertebrate evolution. Unlike mammals, fetal Leydig cells are
26 absent from the early gonads of *T. scripta*, where the supporting lineage expresses genes
27 required for androgen synthesis. Evolutionary reconstructions show that this lineage derives
28 from a *Pax2*-positive mesenchymal population, suggesting an ancestral condition in
29 Archelosauria that differs from the primarily coelomic epithelium origin in the mammalian
30 clade. Transcriptional dynamics and co-expression analyses revealed the recruitment of
31 lineage-specific transcription factors, including *Twist1* or *Runx1*, into the genetic programs of
32 vertebrate clades. Our findings reveal extensive plasticity of the cellular and genetic
33 mechanisms of vertebrate sex determination and suggest that this flexibility is a key feature
34 of gonadal evolution.

35

36 MAIN TEXT

37 INTRODUCTION

38 Sex determination is the process by which an initially bipotential gonad commits to
39 either the ovarian or testicular fate. This process is paramount for sexual reproduction but,
40 despite this importance, sex determination mechanisms can evolve fast even within
41 vertebrates ¹. In animals with genetic sex determination (GSD), sex is determined by the
42 presence or absence of a sex chromosome. That is the case for mammals that display an
43 XY sex determination system (males are XY) ^{2,3} or birds which have a ZW sex determination
44 system (females are ZW) ⁴. In addition to the different varieties of GSD, numerous vertebrate
45 species determine sex through environmental cues that can include social interactions, food
46 availability or pH. One of the most prevalent environmental mechanisms is
47 temperature-dependent sex determination (TSD), which has been described in a wide range
48 of animal species including turtles and alligators ⁵. Despite the remarkable variety of inputs
49 that can initiate sex determination, the gonads of vertebrates share similarities at the
50 morphological, physiological and gene expression levels. ⁶ Those observations led to the
51 hypothesis that the cell types, developmental processes and genetic programs underlying
52 sex determination are mostly conserved, even when they may respond to different initial
53 triggers.⁷

54 Recent single-cell RNA-seq studies in model organisms, like mouse ^{8,9} or chicken ¹⁰ ,
55 have contributed to finely delineate the cell types and lineages involved in sex determination.
56 Three main cell lineages are distinguished: germ cells, supporting cells and interstitial cells.
57 Supporting cells, which differentiate into either Sertoli in males or granulosa cells in females,
58 are of special interest. They pioneer sex determination in all studied vertebrate species and
59 instruct the rest of the gonad, including germ cells, towards the testicular or the ovarian fate
60 ¹¹. Importantly, the supporting cell lineages of mice and chickens have a different
61 developmental origin. In mouse gonads, Sertoli and granulosa cells derive primarily from the
62 coelomic epithelium ^{8,9,12}, while in chicken and other birds they originate from mesenchymal
63 cells that express the transcription factor (TF) Pax2 ^{10,13}. Interestingly, a new cell type called
64 supporting like cells (SLC) has been recently described in mammals ¹⁴. These cells are
65 similar transcriptomically to supporting cells, but express the TF PAX8. SLCs mostly
66 contribute to the formation of the rete testis and rete ovarii, but they also constitute a minor
67 source of Sertoli and granulosa cells. Of relevance are also the fetal Leydig cells of the
68 mammalian testis, derived from the interstitial lineage ¹⁵, which are responsible for the
69 production of androgens from cholesterol during prenatal stages ¹⁶. Estrogens, produced
70 through the aromatase-mediated conversion of androgens¹⁷, have been also reported to be

71 synthesized in the prenatal ovaries of some mammalian species, such as human or rabbits,
72 although the specific cell type responsible for this activity remains uncertain. While sex
73 steroids are dispensable for sex determination in mammals ¹⁸, they play a more prominent
74 role modulating gonadal fate in non-mammalian vertebrate species, with their manipulation
75 often leading to gonadal sex reversal. That is the case in chicken, where androgens are
76 produced by fetal Leydig cells in testes and theca cells in ovaries, but converted into
77 estrogens exclusively in the ovaries by granulosa cells. Importantly, Leydig cells and theca
78 cells in the chicken appear to derive from supporting cells and not from the interstitial
79 lineage, as described for mammals ¹⁰. Taken together, these findings indicate divergence in
80 the origin of supporting and steroidogenic gonadal cell types across vertebrate evolution.

81 To extend our understanding of the evolution of the gonad to vertebrates that lack
82 sex chromosomes and instead rely on TSD systems, we directed our attention to the
83 red-eared slider turtle *Trachemys scripta*. *T. scripta* displays a warm-female/cool-male TSD
84 system, so constant warm (31°C) incubations give rise to female offspring while cool (26°C)
85 incubations promote exclusively male offspring ¹⁹. Temperature and sex are linked via the
86 phosphorylation of Stat3 in response to the influx of calcium at 31°C. pSTAT3 then promotes
87 ovarian differentiation through the repression of *Kdm6b* and its target, *Dmrt1* ²⁰. Additionally,
88 sex hormones can play a pivotal role, as demonstrated by the sex reversal phenotypes
89 obtained upon pharmacological or genetic manipulation of androgen and estrogen levels
90 ^{21,22}. Here, to clarify the evolution of the cell types and genetic programs underlying gonadal
91 sex determination and differentiation, we employed single-cell RNA-seq to investigate cell
92 lineages and their origins during TSD in *T. scripta*. Crucially, we put our results in the
93 context of available datasets from vertebrates with GSD (chicken ¹⁰ and mouse ^{8,9}). We
94 found that, although coarse cell lineages are conserved among all vertebrates studied,
95 striking differences were evident at the level of cell types and origins, cell differentiation
96 mechanisms and genetic programs.

97 RESULTS

98 Transcriptional dynamics during TSD in single cells

99 To shed light on the cellular and molecular mechanisms behind sex determination in
100 response to temperature, we carried out single-cell RNA-seq experiments in gonads from *T.*
101 *scripta* embryos around the thermosensitive period. Embryos were incubated at either the
102 male-promoting temperature (MPT) of 26 °C or the female-promoting temperature (FPT) of
103 31°C (Fig. 1a). Gonadal samples were collected at Greenbaum Stg.15, Stg.18 and Stg.23
104 which corresponds to undifferentiated, sex-determining and differentiated gonads (testes and
105 ovaries respectively). Altogether, we sequenced a total of 25,748 cells from six different
106 conditions. Single-cell transcriptomes from the different experiments were integrated for
107 dimensionality reduction and clustering, obtaining 26 different clusters (see methods,
108 Extended Data Fig. 1a). Consistent with *a priori* expectations, we found more similar cell
109 compositions among Stg.15 gonadal samples raised at either MPT or FPT (prior to the sex
110 determination window). In contrast, gonads from the latest stage Stg. 23 displayed clusters
111 of cells that were clearly sex-specific (Fig. 1b, Extended Data Fig. 1b).

112 To assign identity to each gonadal cell cluster we performed differential expression
113 analysis to obtain marker genes (Extended Data Fig. 2), focusing on transcription factors
114 (TF). Using a combination of GSEA GO enrichment analysis (Extended Data Fig. 3) and
115 available literature we identified 16 different cell types with clearly distinct transcriptional
116 signatures (Fig. 1c-d, Extended Data Fig. 2). Germ cells, studied extensively in a previous
117 publication²³, were recognized by the expression of known markers like *Dazl* or *Piwi1* and
118 the enrichment of GO terms like *meiotic cell cycle*. Cell types belonging to the somatic
119 portion of the gonad were identified using the known marker *Gata4* (Fig. 1e). Among the
120 *Gata4*⁺ cells we identified (i) cells from the coelomic epithelium expressing epithelial
121 markers like *Cd109* and high levels of the TFs *Lhx9* and *Emx2*, (ii) interstitial cells
122 expressing collagen and extracellular-matrix related genes (i.e. *Col6a3* and *Dcn*) and (iii)
123 cells from the supporting lineage. Supporting progenitor cells from early stages are
124 distinguished by the expression of *Dmrt1* and *Sox9* (Fig. 1e). These TFs continue to be
125 expressed in the two clusters of Sertoli cells, characterized also by the expression of the
126 *Amh* gene encoding for the anti-mullerian hormone (Fig. 1e). In contrast, *Dmrt1* and *Sox9*
127 are downregulated in the two distinct clusters of granulosa cells which express the
128 aromatase encoding gene *Cyp19a1* (Fig. 1e) and the TF *Foxl2*. We also identified
129 *Gata4*-negative (*Gata4*⁻) cell types like *Cldn5/Sox18*⁺ endothelial cells (enriched in
130 angiogenesis GO terms) and mesenchymal cell populations that were either *Pax2/Tbx1*⁺
131 (*Pax2*⁺ mes.) or *Tcf21*⁺ (*Pax2*⁻ mes. I and II, enriched in extracellular matrix remodelling GO
132 terms). Importantly, *Gata4*⁻ mesenchymal cell clusters were only observed at early stages of

133 both MPT and FPT gonads. Finally, additional clusters of extragonadal cell types were also
134 distinguished. Those include *Mrap/Hsd11b2*⁺ non-gonadal steroidogenic cells (expressing
135 genes related with melanocortin and cortisol signalling), *Phox2b/Tfap2b*⁺ sympathetic
136 peripheral neurons (GO term *neurotransmitter transport*), *Hnf1b/Kcnj16*⁺ mesonephric tubule
137 cells (enriched in GO terms related to ion transport) and *C1qb/C1qb*⁺ immune cells (immune
138 system related GO terms). We further validated relevant signatures within *T. scripta* gonads
139 through immunofluorescence, confirming the spatial distribution of the somatic *Gata4*⁺
140 populations, germ cells and the supporting lineage (Fig. 1h; Extended Data Fig. 4).

141

142 **Figure 1. Temperature-dependent sex determination at the single cell scale.** a) Diagram of
 143 bipotential gonad differentiation in either testis or ovaries in response to cold MPT or warm FPT
 144 respectively. Cells from critical stages before, during and after the sex determination were collected
 145 from single-cell RNA-seq. b) UMAP projection after the integration of the six different samples: 3

146 stages at FPT and 3 stages of MPT. Lighter colors represent earlier stages. c) Same UMAP projection
147 colored by the different cell types identified after Leiden clustering. d) Dotplot displaying the
148 expression of the top 3 non-redundant markers per cell type. The size of the dot represents the
149 percentage of the cells expressing the gene in each cell type and the color the mean expression. e)
150 SCVI normalized expression of the genes *Gata4*, *Dmrt1*, *Amh* and *Cyp19a1* projected on the UMAP.
151 f) MA plot from the differential expression analysis between MPT and FPT in the cell type Supporting
152 progenitors. The x-axis represents the logarithm of the maximum mean expression and the y-axis the
153 fold change. Negative values of fold changes correspond to genes more expressed in FPT. Genes
154 upregulated in FPT are highlighted in red and genes upregulated in MPT in blue. Transcription factors
155 (TFs) and members of the GO term *response to temperature stimulus* are squared black and green
156 respectively g) SCVI normalized expression of *Kdm6b*, *Dmrt1*, *Twist1*, *Sox9* and *Foxl2* in cell types of
157 the supporting lineage. h) Representative immunofluorescence images of gonadal cross sections from
158 St.15 and St.18 incubated at FPT and MPT. Twist1 is labeled in cyan, Sox9 in red, and HuC/D
159 (labelling germ cells) in green. The gonad is outlined with white dashed line (scalebar, 25 μ m). i)
160 Combined AUCell scores of the gene set composed by the genes belonging to the GO term *response*
161 *to cold* in each cell type at either FPT or MPT.

162

163 After assigning cell type identities, we investigated early differences between FPT
164 and MPT gonads in the supporting progenitors to identify uncharacterized TSD determinants
165 in turtles. We performed differential expression analysis and identified only 9 and 16 genes
166 upregulated in FPT and MPT supporting cells respectively (Fig. 1f). Previous works
167 proposed that the first sexually dimorphic event at the transcriptional level in *T. scripta* is the
168 downregulation of *Kdm6b* and *Dmrt1* in FPT in response to phosphorylated Stat3
169 (pSTAT3)²⁰. Consistently, we found an MPT biased expression of *Kdm6b* and *Dmrt1* in
170 supporting progenitors, although differences were not statistically significant (Fig. 1g). Next
171 we manually inspected the 25 differentially expressed genes (DEG) across all clusters and
172 pinpointed those genes whose differences in expression were restricted to the supporting
173 lineage (Extended Data Fig. 5). We found 2 FPT biased genes (*Twist1*, *Dnaja4*) and 5 MPT
174 biased genes (*Atp6ap2*, *Cryab*, *Adm2*, *Susd1* and *Gfra3*). We specifically focused on *Twist1*
175 as it is the only transcription factor that was significantly upregulated in our single-cell
176 analysis (Fig. 1g) and it has not been linked to sex determination. Furthermore, *Twist1*
177 expression in female supporting cells precedes *Foxl2* expression and Sox9 downregulation
178 (Fig. 1g), suggesting that it operates early. We characterized the expression pattern of
179 *Twist1* through immunofluorescence (Fig. 1h, Extended Data Fig. 6a) and confirmed its
180 FPT-biased expression. In the supporting lineage of FPT gonads, *Twist1* expression starts
181 from Stg.15 and peaks at Stg.18, gradually decreasing expression after Stg.19 when the
182 gonad starts to display clear patterns of ovarian differentiation (Extended Data Fig. 6b). In
183 contrast, *Twist1* was not detected via immunofluorescence in MPT gonads from Stg.15-23.

184 Co-immunofluorescence with the testicular marker Sox9 revealed that the expression of
185 Sox9 precedes Twist1 expression in the supporting lineage of FPT gonads at early stages.
186 Yet, both markers colocalize extensively through Stgs.16-17 and resolve to Twist+/Sox9-
187 cells at FPT Stgs.18-19. These dynamic expression patterns are compatible with an
188 antagonistic relationship between Sox9 and Twist1, as it has been reported during
189 chondrogenesis in mouse ²⁴. Next, we explored the conservation of *Twist1* expression in
190 supporting cells in other vertebrate species by evaluating its expression in publicly available
191 datasets (Extended Data Fig. 6c-d). We found that *Twist1* was not expressed in supporting
192 cells in chicken or mouse (Extended Data Fig. 6e-f), suggesting that a putative role in sex
193 determination could be restricted to turtles.

194 To identify sexually dimorphic biological processes, we used Gene Set Enrichment
195 Analysis (GSEA) in supporting cells at either FPT or MPT. This analysis revealed 106 GO
196 terms upregulated between gonads incubated at distinct temperatures (Extended Data Fig.
197 7). At FPT, we found 22 GO terms enriched related to core cellular processes like synthesis
198 of DNA and protein and cellular respiration. In contrast, the 84 terms enriched at MPT
199 revealed the activation of processes related to morphogenesis and development (i.e. *cell*
200 *morphogenesis*, *cell migration*, *cell junction organization* or *negative chemotaxis*) and with
201 the physiology of more mature Sertoli cells (i.e. *response to hormone*, *lipid transport*,
202 *regulated exocytosis*). Suggestively, GO terms like *MAPK cascade* (involved in male sex
203 determination in mice ²⁵), *phosphatidylinositol metabolism* and *response to endoplasmic*
204 *reticulum stress* (both tightly linked with Ca²⁺ signalling) were also upregulated in MPT
205 supporting cells (Extended Data Fig. 7). The latter could be activated in response to defects
206 in protein folding following cold incubation temperatures. Indeed, among the DEGs we found
207 two genes (*Cryab* and *Dnaja4*) related to *protein folding* and *response to temperature* which
208 prompted us to investigate the molecular response to temperature further. We found
209 individual genes involved in processes like *response to temperature stimulus*, *response to*
210 *heat* and *response to cold* that were expressed across all gonadal cell types (Extended Data
211 Fig. 8a), but were most highly represented in the supporting lineage (Extended Data Fig.
212 8b). In particular, the combined expression of *response to cold* genes (calculated with
213 AUCCell ²⁶) was higher in MPT supporting lineage cells in comparison with FPT cells or MPT
214 cells from other cell types (Fig. 1i). This suggests that cells of the supporting lineage might
215 be particularly sensitive to temperature changes. To investigate this aspect further, we
216 explored the expression of the temperature dependent Trpv Ca²⁺ channels, implicated in
217 TSD in alligators ²⁷. We found that *Trpv4* and *Trpv5-6* were expressed in supporting cells
218 (Extended Data Fig. 8c), suggesting a conserved role as temperature sensing channels in
219 TSD.

220 Evolution of the genetic programs across vertebrate gonadal cell types

221 Sex determination mechanisms diverge among vertebrate clades (i.e. TSD in *T.*
222 *scripta*, XY GSD in mammals and ZW GSD in birds). Yet, our initial comparisons of
223 single-cell data from gonads of turtle, mouse and chicken suggested homologies across
224 most gonadal cell types, as denoted by the expression of common marker genes (Fig. 1c,
225 Extended Data Fig. 6c-d). Although it was possible to infer the overall conservation of the
226 main critical lineages, germ cells, supporting cells and interstitial cells, notable exceptions
227 were mouse fetal Leydig cells and theca cells of chicken ovaries, which had no obvious
228 counterparts in turtle gonads.

229 To investigate the degree of conservation of the genetic programs that define the
230 identity of critical gonadal cell types we used Weighted Correlation Network Analysis
231 (WGCNA) ^{28,29}. First, we focused on the comparison between gonads of turtles and chickens,
232 as these species are closer phylogenetically. We obtained 10 WGCNA coexpression
233 modules in chickens ¹⁰ (Fig. 2a), together with their consensus expression profiles known as
234 their module eigengenes (ME). This metric helped us to recognize that 9 out of the 10
235 modules were associated with particular cell-types (Extended Data Fig. 9a) and were named
236 accordingly (Fig. 2a). To further characterize WGCNA modules, we explored the genes
237 associated with them by ranking them according to the similarity of their expression profile to
238 the ME of each module, a metric referred to as the gene ME connectivity (kME). Genes with
239 high kME values are more associated with a particular module and were thus considered as
240 hub genes. This analysis facilitated the identification of the module without a clear
241 association with a cell type, as a cell cycle module (Extended Data Fig. 9b). In addition, the
242 identification of hub genes confirmed the presence of known regulators of gonad
243 development within the different WGCNA modules. For instance, *Foxl2/Cyp19a1/Sall1*
244 appeared as hub genes of the *granulosa* module, *Amh/Sox9* in *Sertoli*, and the androgen
245 producing enzymes *Star/Cyp11a1/Cyp17a1* in the *Theca* module (Extended Data Fig. 9b).
246 Next, we explored the degree of conservation of chicken WGCNA modules in turtles. For this
247 purpose, we used 1-to-1 orthologs to recalculate ME in our single-cell datasets from turtle
248 gonads. We discovered that 5 out of the 9 modules (*Supporting lineage*, *Sertoli*, *granulosa*,
249 *Interstitial prog.* and *Interstitial*) displayed higher ME values in the expected putatively
250 homologous cell type (Fig. 2b), suggesting at least a partial conservation of cell types and
251 genetic programs across species. Of the 4 remaining modules, 3 were related with the
252 coelomic epithelium and the ovarian cortex of chicken which are highly specialized
253 (*Coelomic epithelium I and II* and *Ovarian cortex*). The remaining module was the *Theca*,
254 which was not associated with a particular cell type as observed in chicken. In contrast, this

255 module displayed higher ME scores across all the cell types of the turtle supporting lineage,
256 suggesting a distribution of the steroidogenic role among several cell types.

257 To further investigate the cross-species conservation of WGCNA modules, we
258 obtained conservation metrics using NetRep³⁰. These metrics fall into two main categories:
259 density and connectivity. In this context, density metrics evaluate whether the genes grouped
260 into a WGCNA module in one species remain coexpressed in the second species. In
261 contrast, connectivity metrics evaluate whether the relationships between the genes in the
262 module are maintained (i.e. their relative importance). It is worth noting that the conservation
263 at the connectivity level of a module that is not conserved at the density level is difficult to
264 interpret biologically, and therefore we focused on density metrics first. Here, 5 out of the 10
265 WGCNA modules calculated in chicken were found to be conserved in turtles at the density
266 level (*Supporting*, *Sertoli*, *granulosa*, *Interstitial* and *Cell cycle*) and 4 of them were also
267 conserved at the connectivity level (excluding *Supporting*, Fig. 2c, Extended Data Fig. 10).
268 We then performed the converse analysis and identified 17 WGCNA modules in turtles. A
269 total of 9 modules could be assigned to one or several turtle cell types, while the remaining
270 ones displayed a pervasive distribution across cell types, including a cell cycle module
271 (Extended Data Fig. 11). 6 out of the 9 cell-type specific modules displayed higher ME
272 values in the homologous chicken cell types, including the *Coelomic epithelium* module
273 which corresponded to the Coelomic epithelium and Ovarian cortex clusters (Extended Data
274 Fig. 12a). Seemingly inconsistent with these results, NetRep conservation analysis only
275 identified three WGCNA modules of turtles conserved in chicken at the density level
276 (*Supporting I*, *Mesonephros-Interstitial* and *Cell cycle*) and the module *Supporting I* was not
277 conserved at the connectivity level (Extended Data Fig. 12b). Unexpectedly, the modules
278 *Sertoli* and *granulosa* calculated in chicken were conserved in turtles and not vice versa. We
279 hypothesized that core genetic programs identified in the Sertoli and granulosa cells of
280 chicken are conserved also in *T. scripta*. However, additional genes were incorporated
281 independently in the turtle supporting cell lineage modules.

282 In order to pinpoint genes that were incorporated specifically into *T. scripta* genetic
283 programs, we focused on genes that were highly associated to a turtle module but lost this
284 association in chicken. This analysis revealed several examples of turtle specific genes like
285 the TF *Tbx1*, which is highly associated with the *Supporting I* module in turtles but not in
286 chicken (Fig. 2d). Accordingly, *Tbx1* was expressed specifically in supporting progenitor cells
287 and *Pax2+* mes. cells in turtles and lacks this cell type specificity in chicken (Fig. 2e-f).
288 Likewise, the TF *Nkx3-1* and the signalling molecule *Wnt16* were exclusively associated with
289 the *T. scripta* modules *Sertoli* and *granulosa* respectively (Extended Data Fig. 12c-h). Hence,

290 cross-species WGCNA analysis not only allowed us to identify which genetic circuits are
 291 conserved, but to single out species-specific acquisitions associated with cell type evolution.

292

293

294 **Figure 2. The evolution of the genetic programs of gonadal cell types in vertebrates.** a) UMAP
295 projection in which each dot represents a chicken gene in a WGCNA module. Coexpressed genes are
296 grouped together. The name of the top TFs per module are shown. b) Heatmap showing Module
297 Eigengene (ME) scores of chicken WGCNA modules in each of the *T. scripta* cell types. High ME
298 scores imply that the genes of the chicken WGCNA module are active in the corresponding cell type
299 of *T. scripta*. Rectangles highlight chicken WGCNA modules that are active in putatively homologous
300 cell types in both chicken and *T. scripta*. c) Lollipop plot displaying network conservation FDR values
301 between chicken and *T. scripta* of the different WGCNA modules calculated with NetRep. On the
302 x-axis is represented the negative logarithm of the FDR of a permutation test assessing whether the
303 module has a higher conservation metric than modules generated by chance. Density conservation
304 metrics (top) assess whether the genes that are coexpressed in the WGCNA module in chicken are
305 also coexpressed in *T. scripta*. Connectivity preservation metrics (bottom) assess whether the
306 hierarchy of the module is conserved, e.g the genes more central to the module in chicken are also
307 central in *T. scripta*. The size of the lollipop circle is proportional to the number of genes in the
308 module. d) Scatterplot showing the membership (kME) of the genes belonging to the WGCNA module
309 *Supporting I* calculated in *T. scripta* both in *T. scripta* (y-axis) and chicken (x-axis). Most of the genes in
310 the module have kME scores that are greater than 0 in chicken indicating that the module is
311 conserved (labeled black, i.e. *Dmrt1*, *Sox9*). Genes that are associated in *T. scripta* but not in chicken
312 (KME differences above the third quartile plus 1.5 times the interquartile range) are labeled green (i.e.
313 *Tbx1*). e-f) SCVI normalized expression of *Tbx1* in *T. scripta* and chicken cell types respectively. g) As
314 in a), UMAP projection of the genes grouped by WGCNA module calculated in mouse. h) As in b)
315 heatmap showing ME scores of mouse WGCNA modules in *T. scripta* cell types. i) As in c) lollipop
316 plot showing NetRep network conservation metrics of mouse WGCNA modules in *T. scripta*. j) As in
317 d) for the genes of the *T. scripta* module *Supporting II* in *T. scripta* (y-axis) and mouse (x-axis). k-l)
318 SCVI normalized expression of *Esr1* in *T. scripta* and mouse cell types respectively.

319

320 Next, we wondered if the moderate conservation of modules and cell types between
321 turtles and birds could be also expanded to mammals. We performed analogous analyses in
322 mouse gonads and found 32 WGCNA modules, 10 of them being associated with cell types
323 (Fig. 2g, Extended Data Fig. 13). Notably, when we assessed the expression of these
324 modules of genes in turtles we could recognize coarse cell lineages (Fig. 2h, Extended Data
325 Fig. 14a). For instance, ME values for the mouse modules Sertoli and granulosa were not
326 directly associated with the corresponding cell types in turtles, but rather peaked equally in
327 all cell clusters belonging to the supporting lineage. Similarly, the mouse modules
328 *Mesonephros*, *Interstitial* and *Mesonephros-interstitial* peaked in both turtle populations.
329 Taken together, these data suggest the presence of homologous cell lineages and genetic
330 circuits operating in both *T. scripta* and mammals. Nevertheless, as expected, those lineages
331 and circuits are more divergent than in the comparison with chicken. Indeed, we interrogated

332 the conservation of the coexpression modules using NetRep and found that 5 out of the 10
333 modules (*Supporting*, *Sertoli*, *Interstitial*, *Mesonephros*, *Mesonephros-interstitial*) were
334 conserved at the density level, however, only the last one (*Mesonephros-interstitial*) was
335 conserved at the connectivity level (Fig. 2i, Extended Data Fig. 14b). Among the modules
336 with lower conservation scores we found both the *Fetal Leydig* cell, with no clear counterpart
337 in turtles, but also the *granulosa* module. We analyzed the source of the lack of conservation
338 of the module *granulosa* in turtles (Extended Data Fig. 14c). Among other genes, the hub
339 TFs *Runx1* and *Irx3*, were absent or lowly expressed in *T. scripta* granulosa cells during the
340 sex determination window (Extended Data Fig. 14d-g). This finding was surprising because
341 the TF *Runx1* has a well studied, conserved role in the specification of granulosa cells, from
342 mammals to teleost fishes³¹. We took advantage of a well defined list of Runx1 targets in
343 mouse ovaries to further explore the potential dismantling of the Runx1-driven genetic
344 program in *T. scripta*. To this end we interrogated the expression of RUNX1 targets in mouse
345 and turtles embryonic gonads (Extended Data Fig. 15a-b). In mice, the combined expression
346 of RUNX1 targets mirrors that of the transcription factor: active in granulosa cells and
347 supporting progenitors and absent from Sertoli cells. In contrast, in *T. scripta* gonads where
348 Runx1 is not detected, Runx1 targets are expressed broadly and the female specific
349 expression in granulosa cells is lost. Additionally, we could identify a set of 12 targets (i.e.
350 *Ryr2*, *Mmp15*, *Mettl24*) that were clearly associated with the module *granulosa* in mice but
351 not in turtles (Extended Data Fig. 15c). These analyses suggest that *Runx1* may have lost its
352 role as an ovarian differentiation factor in turtles.

353 Finally, we performed the converse analysis, and recalculated WGNA modules in
354 turtles to assess their conservation in mice (Extended Data Fig. 16a-b). We found that only
355 the module *Mesonephros-Interstitial* was conserved both at the density and connectivity level
356 and the *Supporting I* only at the density level (driven by common hub genes such as *Dmrt1*,
357 *Sox9* and *Nr5a1*, Extended Data Fig. 16c). The divergence between modules of the
358 supporting lineage between mouse and turtles prompted us again to identify turtle-specific
359 genetic modules involved in sex determination. In the case of Sertoli cells, we found again
360 the turtle-specific association of the transcription factor *Nkx3-1* with the *Sertoli* module
361 (Extended Data Fig. 16d-e). In the more divergent module *granulosa* (Extended Data Fig.
362 16f), genes such as *Ar* and *Cyp19a1* were also uniquely associated in turtles (Extended
363 Data Fig. 16 g-j). Finally, *Esr1* showed a turtle-specific association with the module
364 *Supporting II* (Fig. 2j-l). The central role of genes related to the synthesis (*Cyp19a1*) and
365 response (*Ar*, *Esr1*) of androgens and estrogens in turtles reflect the importance of steroid
366 hormones for sex differentiation in non mammalian vertebrates. Taken together, WGCNA
367 results indicate that the genetic programs responsible for the specification of critical cell

368 lineages in sex determination across vertebrates are sufficiently similar to establish cell type
369 homologies. However, they have been heavily reconfigured in the different lineages
370 independently, including the turnover of critical transcription factors. Illustrative examples of
371 this turnover are the incorporation of *Tbx1* or *Nkx3.1* and the loss of importance of *Runx1* or
372 *Irx3* in *T. scripta* gonads.

373

374 **Supporting cells mediate fetal steroidogenesis in turtles**

375 Our WGCNA analyses revealed a lack of conservation of the steroidogenic modules
376 *Theca* of chicken and *Fetal Leydig* of mouse, that were not assigned to any specific cell type
377 of turtles (Fig. 2c,i). This result is remarkable, given that steroid hormones play during sex
378 determination in turtles. To identify which cell populations are responsible for steroidogenesis
379 in this species, we scored the expression of the genes of the modules *Theca* and *Fetal*
380 *Leydig* in turtle cells. The ME scores of both modules indicated a moderate enrichment in
381 clusters derived from the supporting lineage (e.g. Supporting progenitors, Sertoli and
382 granulosa cells, Fig. 3a-b). For instance *Star*, which encodes the first enzyme required for
383 androgen synthesis, was expressed specifically in the clusters Supporting progenitors,
384 granulosa and Sertoli (Fig. 3c). Similarly, the genes that encode the enzymes that convert
385 cholesterol into androgens (e.g. *Cyp11a1*, *Hsd3b* and *Cyp17a1*) were also predominantly
386 expressed in cells of the supporting lineage (Fig. 3d-f). The aromatase gene *Cyp19a1*,
387 responsible for the conversion of androgens into estrogens, was expressed exclusively in
388 female granulosa cells (Fig. 3g). We employed immunofluorescence to validate the
389 coexpression of the steroidogenic enzyme *Cyp11a1* with the somatic and supporting cell
390 markers *Gata4* and *Sox9* respectively in FPT and MPT gonads (Fig. 3h and Extended Data
391 Fig. 17). In contrast to mammals, *Cyp11a1* staining was found in supporting cells at both
392 MPT and FPT within the primitive sex cords, denoted by its colocalization with *Sox9*, but not
393 in the gonadal interstitium. Importantly we do not observe this colocalization outside the
394 gonad, where *Cyp11a1*⁺ cells do not express *Sox9*. From an evolutionary perspective (Fig.
395 3i), androgens are produced in mammalian species by interstitial fetal Leydig cells and
396 exclusively in males. In chicken, there are also cell types specialized in the synthesis of
397 androgens, termed fetal theca in females and fetal Leydig in males¹⁰. Yet, in contrast to
398 mammals, both populations are derived from the supporting lineage (pre-Sertoli cells in
399 males and pregranulosa cells in the female¹⁰). In turtles the situation is more similar to
400 chicken, since steroidogenic enzymes are also produced by supporting lineage cells.
401 However, *T. scripta* seems to lack a specialized population undertaking androgen
402 production. Rather, genes encoding steroid enzymes are expressed broadly in both

403 undifferentiated supporting progenitor cells and more mature Sertoli and granulosa cells.
 404 These results show that analogous functions, in this case steroidogenesis, can be performed
 405 by different gonadal lineages across vertebrate clades.

406
 407 **Figure 3. Steroidogenesis in *T. scripta* gonads.** a-b) Module Eigengene (ME) scores of the
 408 WGCNA modules *Theca* and *Fetal Leydig* of chicken and mouse respectively in *T. scripta* cell types.
 409 c-g) SCVI normalized expression of genes encoding fundamental enzymes involved in the synthesis
 410 of androgens and estrogens. h) Representative immunofluorescence images of MPT and FPT
 411 gonadal cross sections at St.18. DAPI labels the nuclei in grey, Sox9 labels the supporting cells in
 412 cyan, and Cyp11a1 labels steroidogenic cells in red. Note that Cyp11a1 labels the cytoplasm of Sox9+
 413 cells at both temperatures (scalebar, 25 μ m) and that Cyp11a1+/Sox9- cells are located outside the
 414 gonad (delineated with a white dashed line). The yellow box depicts the region magnified on the right
 415 break-out panels. i) Diagram summarizing the process of sex hormone synthesis in different
 416 vertebrates with the cell type in charge of its production.

417

418 A mesenchymal Pax2+ origin of the supporting lineage in Archelosauria

419 As described above, the supporting lineage in turtles is characterized by the
 420 expression of lineage-specific genes that have been extensively characterized in mammals,

421 such as *Sox9* for Sertoli cells or *Foxl2* for granulosa cells. Yet, turtle supporting cells are also
 422 steroidogenic, denoting functional differences between homologous cell types across major
 423 vertebrate clades. Notably, the supporting lineage in chickens, which also has steroidogenic
 424 potential, originates from mesenchymal cells that express the transcription factor Pax2.^{10,13}
 425 This contrasts with the developmental origin described in mice for this lineage. In this
 426 species, the supporting lineage mostly derives from the coelomic epithelium^{8,9,12}, with a
 427 minor contribution from SLC progenitors^{15,32}. Therefore, we explored whether the origin of
 428 the supporting cells in turtles is more similar to the condition described in mammals or birds.

429

430 **Figure 4. Pax2+ mesenchymal origin of supporting lineage cells in *T. scripta*.** a) PAGA trajectory
 431 analysis of FPT somatic gonad cells. On the left, UMAP embedding from a subcluster of FPT somatic
 432 cells displaying information of the stage at which they were sampled. In the middle, the same UMAP

433 embedding but this time colored according to the Leiden subclusters. Subclusters composed of a
434 majority of Stg. 23 cells are considered terminal and marked with a squared flag. The widths of the
435 connections between clusters represent the PAGA scores. Higher PAGA scores suggest a more likely
436 transition between two cell types. The shortest path from Pax2+ mesenchymal cells to granulosa cells
437 is represented with black lines, the rest of connections are shown as discontinuous grey lines. On the
438 right, the barplot represents the shortest distances between early clusters and terminal clusters of
439 granulosa cells. b) Same as i a) but for MPT somatic cells. On the right, shortest distances between
440 early clusters and terminal clusters of Sertoli cells. c) Representative immunofluorescence images of
441 MPT gonadal cross sections at St.18. β -catenin (CTNNB1) is labeled in cyan, Sox9 in red, and Pax2
442 in green. The yellow box depicts the region magnified on the break-out panels. The white arrows point
443 to cells of the gonad which co-express Sox9 and Pax2 (scalebar, 25 μ m). d) Diagram showing an
444 evolutionary scenario in which supporting cells of *T. scripta*, similarly to chicken, are mostly derived
445 from Pax2+ mesenchymal cells.

446 Based on our clustering analyses at early stages, we could identify both potential
447 sources for the supporting lineage: cells from the coelomic epithelium (*Lhx9/Emx2+*) and
448 Pax2+ mesenchymal cells (Fig. 1c). While turtle Pax2+ mesenchymal cells also transcribe
449 *Wnt4* and *Osr1* as in chicken (Extended Data Fig. 18a-b), they also display low levels of
450 *Dmrt1*, thus denoting a certain degree of transcriptional divergence. To elucidate the origin of
451 supporting cells in turtles we performed trajectory analysis in MPT and FPT cells separately
452 (Fig. 4a-b). We used a modified version of the PAGA algorithm that takes into account the
453 stage information to infer developmental trajectories (see Methods). Using the PAGA graphs,
454 we calculated the shortest distances from each early-stage cell cluster to each late-stage
455 cluster. As a control, we applied our modified PAGA algorithm to available mouse and
456 chicken datasets and could confirm the previously validated origin of Sertoli and granulosa
457 cells (Pax2+ cells in chicken and coelomic epithelium cells in mouse, Extended Data Figures
458 19-20). In turtle FPT data, we observed that granulosa cells were closer to Pax2+ cells than
459 to coelomic epithelium cells in PAGA graph distances (Fig. 4a); whereas, the coelomic
460 epithelium cells were more related to the ovarian cortex epithelium (Fig. 4a, Extended Data
461 Fig. 18c,e). Similarly, in MPT samples, we observe that Sertoli cells were closer to Pax2+
462 than to coelomic epithelium cells (Fig. 4b, Extended Data Fig. 18d,f). In fact, coelomic
463 epithelium cells were closer to terminal clusters of interstitial cells than to Sertoli cells. Of
464 note, Pax2- mesenchymal cells expressing the transcription factor *Tcf21* were predicted to
465 be a main source of terminal Interstitial cells both in MPT and FPT (Extended Data Fig.
466 18c-f). To further investigate the Pax2+ mesenchymal origin of supporting cells in turtles, we
467 performed immunofluorescence against Pax2 and Sox9 in early MPT and FPT gonads
468 (Stgs.15 and 18). As described in birds, we identified the Pax2+ population adjacent to the
469 mesonephros (Fig. 4c). Importantly, we identified individual cells coexpressing Pax2 and

470 Sox9 at the mesonephric side of the sex cords (Fig. 4c), consistent with bioinformatic
471 predictions that Sox9+ supporting cells in the sex cords derive from Pax2+ cells.

472 Next, we characterized in detail the transcriptomic changes that drive the
473 differentiation of supporting cells. We calculated pseudotimes and analyzed genes that
474 changed expression along the differentiation trajectories connecting Pax2+ mesenchymal
475 cells to 3 different subpopulations of granulosa (Extended Data Fig. 21) and 2
476 subpopulations of Sertoli cells (Extended Data Fig. 22). We first focused on the top 50 most
477 expressed TFs that are dynamically expressed along pseudotime. The initial point of all
478 trajectories leading to either Sertoli or granulosa cells was similar, involving the participation
479 of common TFs such as Pax2, Tbx1, Id1, Meis1 or Nr2f2 whose expression faded later on
480 (Extended Data Fig. 21c, Extended Data Fig. 22c). Importantly, the expression of TFs like
481 Tbx1 is maintained in the transition from Pax2+ mesenchymal cells to supporting
482 progenitors, overlapping with the TFs characteristic of the somatic gonad (i.e. Gata4 and
483 Nr5a1) and supporting progenitors (Sox9). These overlaps in expression are consistent with
484 the coexpression of Pax2 and Sox9 shown by immunofluorescence (Fig. 4c) and further
485 strengthen the idea that early Pax2+ cells become supporting cells at later stages. After this
486 first wave, TFs that are exclusively of bipotential supporting cells such as Stat1, Irf1 or Ctbp1
487 are subsequently expressed. Those TFs coexist with others that are transiently expressed in
488 one of the sexes during the bipotential period, but continue to be expressed in the opposite
489 sex. Examples of the latter are Dmrt1, Sox8, Sox9 and Esr1 which are all expressed at FPT
490 in a narrow temporal window in supporting progenitor cells, but remain expressed throughout
491 Sertoli differentiation at MPT. Conversely, Ar is expressed only briefly at MPT but it is
492 maintained at FPT until granulosa cells are fully differentiated. Eventually, sex specific TFs
493 like Twist1 and Foxl2 in granulosa cells or Nkx3-1 at MPT take over.

494 Based on our observation that the supporting lineage synthesizes sex hormones, we
495 investigated the temporal dynamics of steroidogenic enzyme expression throughout their
496 differentiation. Star, Cyp17a1 and Hsd3b are predominantly expressed in intermediate states
497 of differentiation at FPT, corresponding to bipotential supporting cells (Extended Data Fig.
498 21c). Meanwhile, Cyp11a1 is expressed during the whole process of differentiation to
499 granulosa, although more prominently at early states. Finally, Cyp19a1 is exclusively
500 expressed later on in cells committed to the granulosa fate. Similar to FPT, Cyp17a1 is
501 detected only in the intermediate part of the path of Sertoli differentiation at MPT (Extended
502 Data Fig. 22c). However, Cyp19a1 transcripts are never detected at MPT and Hsd3b and
503 Star expression are maintained in differentiated Sertoli cells. Furthermore, Cyp11a1
504 expression is absent from differentiated Sertoli cells. Finally, we explored the expression of a
505 curated set of genes implicated in the differentiation of granulosa and Sertoli cells in mice³³.

506 As expected, most genes implicated in granulosa differentiation in mice were expressed late
507 in the *Pax2*⁺ mesenchyme to granulosa differentiation trajectory in *T. scripta* (i.e. *Fst*, *Lef1*,
508 *Axin2*) but notable absences were also noticed (i.e. *Rspo1*, *Bmp5*, *Lgr5* and *Irx3* were either
509 not detected or very lowly expressed, Extended Data Fig. 21c). The genes implicated in
510 Sertoli differentiation in mice were also predominantly expressed later on in the *Pax2*⁺
511 mesenchyme to Sertoli in *T. scripta*, with some exceptions such as *Fgf9*, which is only
512 transiently expressed in intermediate states of differentiation in both species (Extended Data
513 Fig. 22c). Altogether, our data show that turtle supporting cells originate primarily from *Pax2*⁺
514 mesenchymal cells, as in birds. This supports a mesenchymal origin as the ancestral
515 condition in Archelosauria and contrasts with the mammalian model, where supporting cells
516 emerge predominantly from the coelomic epithelium (Fig. 4d).

517 DISCUSSION

518 Sex determination mechanisms evolve rapidly within vertebrates, ranging from
519 environmental sex determining systems like those based on temperature (TSD) to genetic
520 sex determination (GSD) ¹. Yet, despite stark differences at the top of sex determining
521 cascades, the overall organization of the testis and ovary organs is similar among
522 vertebrates. Consequently, the cell types, developmental processes and underlying genetic
523 programs involved in sex determination might also be evolutionary conserved ⁷. Here we
524 tested this hypothesis by exploring the cell types and transcriptional programs involved in
525 primary sex determination in a species with TSD, the turtle *T. scripta*, using single-cell
526 transcriptomics. We contextualize our results using equivalent datasets from vertebrate
527 species with GSD: chicken and mouse. By focusing on the expression of known markers
528 and by comparing expression programs across species we confirmed an overall
529 conservation of the main gonadal lineages: germinal, supporting and interstitial. Our results
530 suggest that these three lineages are conserved at least in the last common ancestor of
531 amniotes. However, despite the broad conservation of gonadal lineages across amniotes,
532 we found that the distribution of some gonadal functions differs.

533 An intriguing finding is that *T. scripta* gonads lack fetal Leydig cells, a cell type
534 responsible for androgen production in mammals. The absence of Leydig cells in early turtle
535 gonads is notable, since sex hormones have been repeatedly shown to influence gonadal
536 sex differentiation in *T. scripta* ^{19,21}, and Leydig cells have been described in the adult testes
537 of several turtle species ^{21 34,35}. However, fetal and adult Leydig cells have a different
538 developmental origin, as reported in mammals ¹⁵, consistent with the observations that one
539 of these populations is absent in early prenatal turtle gonads. Here, we show that this critical
540 steroidogenic function in fetal turtle gonads is mediated by the supporting lineage, including
541 progenitors and differentiated Sertoli and granulosa cells. Of note, Sertoli cells in the adult
542 testis of the turtle *C. serpentina* also produce androgens required for spermiogenesis ³⁶ thus
543 confirming that the adult supporting lineage in turtles is competent for the synthesis of
544 steroid hormones. Outside mammals, fetal Leydig cells have only been described in chicken
545 ¹⁰. However, these cells derive from Sertoli cells, in contrast to mammals, where they
546 differentiate from interstitial progenitors. In fact, steroidogenic activity was detected within
547 the sex cords of chicken gonads, and not only in the interstitium. Therefore, the homology
548 between interstitially-derived Leydig cells in mammals and Sertoli-derived steroidogenic cells
549 in birds remains uncertain. Based on these data, we hypothesize that outside mammals,
550 fetal steroidogenesis is driven by supporting-lineage cells with varying levels of
551 specialization, whereas *bona fide* interstitial fetal Leydig cells may represent a mammalian
552 innovation. Thus, in non-mammalian vertebrates, where sex hormones can have a dominant

553 effect on gonadal sex differentiation, these hormones may be synthesized by the same
554 lineage that initiates sex determination: the supporting lineage.

555 Recent single-cell studies of sex determination in *T. scripta* identified a population of
556 thermosensitive steroidogenic cells (TSSCs), proposed to initiate testis development through
557 aldosterone secretion^{37,38}. These studies suggest that TSSCs are located within the
558 developing gonad and are independent of the supporting lineage, based on
559 immunofluorescence analyses of putative TSSC markers (Kcnk3, Cacna1h, and Cacna1c).
560 While we also identify this population in our dataset, multiple lines of evidence indicate that
561 these cells are located outside the gonad, and we therefore refer to them as non-gonadal
562 steroidogenic cells. First, immunofluorescence analyses reveal an almost exclusive
563 colocalization of steroidogenic and supporting cell markers (Cyp11a1 and Sox9,
564 respectively) within the gonad, whereas steroidogenic cells lacking supporting markers are
565 mainly located in the adjacent mesonephros (Fig. 3h). Consistently, non-gonadal
566 steroidogenic cells are detected only at early developmental stages, when mesonephric
567 tissue is included in the dissections, and form a distinct population in UMAP space, with no
568 apparent transcriptional continuity with other somatic gonadal lineages (Fig. 1c). Finally, we
569 find that the proposed TSSC markers Kcnk3, Cacna1h, and Cacna1c are not specific to
570 TSSCs, as they are also expressed in supporting cells, both in our dataset and in the cited
571 studies (see Supplementary Figure 3 of Ye et al.³⁸). Thus, these markers cannot reliably
572 resolve the spatial localization of TSSCs. Yet, despite the noted discrepancy, this collective
573 work supports the notion that steroidogenic cell populations, whether intrinsic to the gonad or
574 closely associated with it, contribute to temperature-dependent sex determination in turtles.

575 The steroidogenic role of the supporting lineage in Archelosauria (turtles and birds)
576 and its contrast with mammals, where these cells do not produce sexual hormones,
577 constitutes an example of functional divergence. These distinct functions may be related to
578 the different developmental origins of these putative homologous cell lineages. As we show,
579 granulosa and Sertoli cells in turtles originate primarily from a Pax2+ mesenchymal
580 population, similar to birds^{10,13}, while most supporting cells arise from the coelomic
581 epithelium in mammals¹². We hypothesize that both progenitor pools had the potency to
582 give rise to supporting lineage cells in the last common ancestor of amniotes. Later, either
583 the coelomic epithelium or the Pax2+ mesenchymal cells may have gained importance in
584 each lineage independently. This hypothesis is supported by the recent discovery of
585 supporting-like cells (SLC) in mammalian gonads^{14,32}. SLCs are similar transcriptomically to
586 supporting cells and they mainly contribute to the formation of the rete testis and rete ovarii
587 in males and females respectively, but they also constitute a minor source of Sertoli and
588 granulosa cells. Interestingly, they are characterized by the expression of the TF Pax8, a

589 close paralog of Pax2 (the PaxB group is composed of *Pax2*, *Pax5* and *Pax8*, which
590 originated in the two rounds of whole genome duplications of vertebrates)³⁹. Alternatively,
591 the capacity of the coelomic epithelium to give rise to supporting cells could have appeared
592 in mammals. A denser taxon sampling within amniotes and also beyond, including
593 amphibians where sex hormones are critical⁴⁰, could help clarify the evolutionary history of
594 supporting lineage cells.

595 Besides differences in cell-type repertoire and origins, we also found divergence in
596 the genetic programs of conserved cell types, involving important lineage-specific regulators
597 such as *Tbx1* or *Esr1*. The absence of *Runx1* expression in turtle granulosa cells, and of
598 several of its direct downstream targets, highlight how gene regulatory networks may
599 reconfigure upon the loss of critical TFs³¹. Particularly striking was the discovery of *Twist1*
600 as the earliest TF acquiring sexual dimorphism during turtle ovarian differentiation, prior to
601 the onset of *Foxl2* expression. While *Twist1* has never been associated with sex
602 determination previously, it has been shown to act as a repressor of the male sex
603 determining gene *Sox9* in the context of chondrogenesis²⁴. Importantly, *Twist1* has been
604 shown to be activated by pStat3 in cancer cell lines⁴¹ and the phosphorylation of Stat3 in
605 response to high temperatures is one of the first known events in ovarian differentiation in *T.*
606 *scripta*. pStat3 was shown to promote ovarian differentiation due to the indirect repression of
607 *Dmrt1* via the repression of the Kdm6b demethylase²⁰. Here we propose that, additionally,
608 pStat3 could promote ovarian differentiation by activating the expression of the
609 female-specific TF *Twist1*. Importantly, pStat3 has also been implicated in the direct
610 activation of the classic female promoting TF *Foxl2*⁴², yet our single cell datasets suggest
611 that the expression of *Twist1* predates *Foxl2* expression in the sex determining cascade of
612 turtles. *Twist1* promotes epithelial to mesenchymal transition (EMT) in embryonic⁴³ and
613 cancer⁴⁴ cell types, which could be important for the reorganization of the primary sex cords
614 in the medulla of the turtle ovary. Overall we found that cell type repertoires, developmental
615 processes and genetic programs involved in vertebrate sex determination are more
616 divergent than previously anticipated. This divergence parallels, to some extent, the turnover
617 of sex determination systems, offering ample regulatory flexibility that may be crucial for
618 species adaptation to changing environments.

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719 Tumor Metastasis. *Cell* **117**, 927–939 (2004).

720 METHODS

721

722 Turtle eggs sampling

723 Freshly laid red-eared slider turtle (*Trachemys scripta elegans*) eggs were
724 obtained from Concordia Turtle Farms (Jonesville, LA) with permission from the Louisiana
725 Department of Agriculture. One day after oviposition, fertilized eggs were randomly
726 distributed into trays of moist perlite and incubated at either 26 °C (male-producing
727 temperature) or 31 °C (female-producing temperature), with humidity maintained at
728 70–80%. To minimize clutch effects, eggs from the same clutches were allocated across
729 treatments. Embryos were staged according to the criteria established by Greenbaum⁴⁵.
730 For all experiments, embryos were removed from the eggshells, immediately decapitated,
731 and transferred to sterile PBS for gonad dissection.

732

733 Single-cell RNA-seq library preparation

734 Eight to twelve pairs of gonads per temperature and stage were pooled for each
735 single-cell RNA-seq experiment. Cell suspensions were prepared using 0.05%
736 Trypsin-EDTA (59417C, Sigma) for 7 min at either MPT or FPT, depending on the sample's
737 original incubation condition. During digestion, tissue was gently pipetted every 2–3 min. The
738 reaction was stopped by adding 5% BSA (B9000S, New England Biolabs), and the
739 suspension was passed through a 40 µm Flowmi cell strainer (15342931, Fisher Scientific).
740 Cells were then collected by centrifugation (300 × g for 5 min at 4 °C), resuspended in PBS
741 for counting and viability assessment, and subsequently fixed by adding methanol (98%)
742 dropwise. Fixed cells were kept on ice for 15 min before being transferred to –80 °C for
743 long-term storage. After rehydration, about 10,000–20,000 cells were loaded on a 10×
744 Chromium controller and sc-RNA libraries were prepared using the Chromium Next Gem
745 Single Cell 3' Reagent Kit v3.1 (PN-1000128) following the manufacturer's instructions.
746 Finally, libraries were sequenced using Illumina NovaSeq 6000 SP with the following
747 parameters: paired-end, 28 + 8 + 91 cycles. The sequencing depth was 200 million reads per
748 sample.

749

750 Single-cell RNA-seq analysis

751 Each *T. scripta* single-cell library was aligned to the *T. scripta* assembly and
752 annotation (CAS_Tse_1.0, GCA_013100865.1) using Cell Ranger. The three prime ends of
753 the genes of the annotation were corrected and extended to improve mapping. Quality
754 control of the cells was performed considering the number of reads and features detected,

755 the percentage of mitochondrial transcripts, and ambient RNA contamination with DecontX⁴⁶.
756 For chicken and mouse, filtered expression matrices were downloaded from GEO (see Data
757 Availability). Doublets were filtered out using scrublet⁴⁷ in all cases. Cells with low fraction of
758 nuclear mRNAs were also filtered out in *T. scripta* and chicken datasets with DropletQC⁴⁸.
759 The different samples within each species were integrated using SCVI⁴⁹
760 (<https://scvi-tools.org/>) and SCVI models were also used for differential expression analysis.
761 The number of latent variables was optimized for both the full gonad by doing a parameter
762 sweep and inspecting the learning curves. Both UMAP dimensionality reductions and leiden
763 clusters were calculated from SCVI latent variables using scanpy⁵⁰. Marker genes for each of
764 the clusters were obtained using SCVI differential expression of each cluster against the
765 rest. GSEA analyses were run on the obtained fold changes of genes that had 1 to 1
766 orthologs with mouse using clusterProfiler⁵¹. Combined scores for particular sets of genes
767 such as genes from a particular GO term were calculated with AUCCell⁵². WGCNA module
768 detection and cross-species comparisons were performed with the package hdWGCNA⁵³
769 following the recommendation of the vignette to choose parameters. Only 1 to 1 orthologs
770 between the species to compare were used both to calculate and to compare the modules.
771 NetRep⁵⁴ was used to assess the conservation of the WGCNA modules, which provide both
772 density and connectivity metrics. In short, density metrics assess whether the genes of the
773 module are also coexpressed in a second species, while connectivity metrics measure
774 whether the hierarchies within the module are maintained. Therefore, we always focus first
775 on the conservation of density metrics. The list of 1 to 1 orthologs was refined by using
776 TOGA⁵⁵ between *T. scripta* and chicken. For trajectory inference, new SCVI models were
777 created using only cells from male or female samples and cell types from the somatic gonad
778 and the mesonephros (excluding germ cells, endothelial cells, kidney, etc.) After reclustering
779 these subsets of gonadal cells, PAGA⁵⁶ was applied to calculate likely transitions between
780 clusters. Then, PAGA connectivities were converted to distances and Dijkstra's algorithm
781 was used to calculate the minimal distance between clusters composed of cells from early
782 stages to cells from later stages. Diffusion components were calculated using destiny⁵⁷ and
783 the pseudotime of the different lineages with slingshot⁵⁸. Genes that were dynamically
784 expressed along the pseudotime and the smoothed expression values were obtained with
785 tradeSeq⁵⁹. Custom R and python code to reproduce the analyses and the figures is
786 available in GitLab (<https://gitlab.com/rdacemel/trachemys-sd>) and contains custom python
787 and R functions gathered in two packages under development, bacarisas
788 (<https://gitlab.com/rdacemel/bacarisas>, for python) and sorolla
789 (<https://gitlab.com/rdacemel/sorolla>, for R) which focus in the production of custom plots.

790

791

792 Immunostaining of cryosections

793 Gonad–mesonephros complexes (GMCs) and whole gonads were dissected in PBS
794 and fixed in 4% PFA (AAJ19943K2, Fisher Scientific) for 30 min rocking at room
795 temperature, then moved through a MeOH gradient to 100% MeOH for long-term storage at
796 -20°C . Samples for cryosection were gradually rehydrated into PBS, moved through a
797 sucrose gradient (10%, 15%, 20%, and 30%), then placed in blocks with OCT medium and
798 moved to -80°C for a minimum of 12 h before cryosectioning. Blocks were serially
799 sectioned at $12\ \mu\text{m}$ and slides were stored at -20°C until ready to use. For immunostaining,
800 sections were rehydrated in PBS, permeabilized in PBST (0.1% Triton X-100), and blocked
801 for 1 h at room temperature (PBS 0.1% TritonX-100, 3% BSA, 10% horse serum). Sections
802 were incubated in primary antibodies diluted in blocking solution at 4°C overnight (Extended
803 Data Table 1). Following three 10-min washes in PBS 0.1% TritonX-100, sections were
804 incubated with secondary antibodies (Cy3 Donkey Anti-rabbit Jackson Immuno Cat#
805 711-165-152; AF488 Donkey Anti-mouse Jackson Immuno Cat# 715-545-150 ; AF647
806 Donkey Anti-goat Jackson Immuno Cat# 705-605-147) at 1:500 dilution and DAPI
807 (62248, Thermo Fisher) diluted in blocking solution for 2 h at room temperature. Following
808 three 10-minute washes in PBST, slides were mounted for imaging with polyvinyl alcohol
809 mounting solution (Catalog #) and stored at 4°C . Sections were imaged using Leica SP8
810 confocal microscope and images were analyzed using FIJI⁶⁰.

811

812 DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

813

814 Single cell RNA-seq (scRNA-seq) data in *T. scripta* have been deposited in GEO
815 repository (GSE271230). Equivalent single cell datasets in chicken and mouse are available
816 under the accessions GSE143337 and GSE184708 respectively.

817

818

819 CODE AVAILABILITY

820

821 The custom R and python code to reproduce the analyses and the figures is
822 available in GitLab (<https://gitlab.com/rdacemel/single-cell-TSD>) and contains custom python
823 and R functions gathered in two packages: *bacarisas* (<https://gitlab.com/rdacemel/bacarisas>,
824 for python) and *sorolla* (<https://gitlab.com/rdacemel/sorolla>, for R) which focus in the
825 production of custom plots.

826

827

828 AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

829

830 R.D.A, B.T., B.C., and D.G.L. conceived the study and designed experiments. B.T.
831 collected and preprocessed Trachemys gonads with the help of C.W.. R.D.A., W.Y.C. and
832 A.H. performed the single-cell RNA-seq experiments. B.T. and S.A. performed
833 immunostainings. R.D.A. analyzed data with inputs from B.T., B.C. and D.G.L.. R.D.A, B.T,
834 B.C and D.G.L wrote the paper with input from all authors.

835

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886 EXTENDED DATA TABLES

887

Antibody	Raised in	Working dilution	Vendor	Cat. No.
Gata4	Goat	1:500	Santa Cruz	SC-1237
Gata4	Mouse	1:500	Santa Cruz	Sc-25310
HuC/ HuD	Mouse	1:50	Thermo Fisher	A-21271
Sox9	Goat	1:500	R&D Systems	AF3075
Lhx9	Goat	1:200	Santa Cruz	SC-19348
Twist1	Rabbit	1:100	Cell Signaling	90445
CTNNB1	Mouse	1:200	Sigma Aldrich	C7207
Laminin	Rabbit	1:500	Gift from Erikson lab (Duke University)	N/A
Pax2/8	Rabbit	1:250	Thermo Fisher	10336-1-ap
Cyp11a1	Rabbit	1:250	Novus	Nbp1-85368

888 **Extended Data Table 1.** Reference of antibodies used in immunofluorescence assays.